

Mixed Reality and BIM applied to Construction Health and Safety

ZAKI AMIRI

Supervisors:

José Granja

University of Minho, ISISE, Department of Civil Engineering, Guimarães, Portugal

Hélder Sousa

University of Minho, ISISE, Department of Civil Engineering, Guimarães, Portugal Ricardo de

Matos Camarinha

Hilti Group, Schaan, Liechtenstein Manuel Luis

BIMTEC, Doha, Qatar

Abstract

In construction, site operations are complex. Construction workers perform a diversity of activities, each often associated with a multitude of risks. Those risks are generally extended to many workers in the vicinity of the operational areas where the activities happen. As such, the construction sector is known for recording a high rate of accidents. Despite the large effort in the analysis of design solutions, planning of activities, education, and awareness of site agents, improvements are required. Our field experience shows that live field CHS management is mostly manual and fragmented. Furthermore, the lack of integration between the digital world and the physical world, especially the interaction between data analysis and the corresponding measures, has led to information fragmentation and data duplication, and stagnation between the different phases of the construction life cycle. events on a construction site are dynamic and constantly changing in terms of facilities, equipment, materials, people, site layout, and various other components at different stages. This increases the complexity of safety monitoring and management of construction sites.

We propose the development of a framework for a Digital Twin application based on a BIM model representing the conditions during the construction stage. This is further enriched with hazards and allows to collection of data from sensors on-site to improve the monitoring

and recording behaviour of construction workers. This framework can be used to create live alerts to one or multiple workers, contributing to mitigating the number of casualties in the industry. Beyond addressing the gap between on-site operation and office controls, Beyond addressing the gap between on-site operation and office controls, our proposal allows creating a database to analyse incidents and inform decisions based on a on the data stores in the BIM model. This model can also be easily updated to better represent each moment of the construction stage (4D BIM), serving as an important tool for the training of those who collaborate in its physical space.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/nIqFe1qJayo>

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